

Impediments to Literary Competence among Selected Grade 12 Learners for whom English is an Additional Language

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Abstract

This article sought to establish factors that impede English literary competence, and to identify challenges Grade 12 teachers and learners encounter in literature. The target population were Grade 12 learners and teachers from five rural schools. The sample constituted of 32 learners and 5 teachers. Learners participated in focus group interviews, while teachers participated in semi-structured interviews. The results indicate that learners fail to explain the effectiveness of literary devices; they cannot back their answers to open-ended questions with textual evidence; they are inactive during literature lessons; they cannot read literary texts independently; and they develop a negative attitude if a text grapples with issues sensitive to them.

Introduction

In South Africa, the National Senior Certificate offers English First Additional Language (EFAL) to a number of learners for whom English is not a home language. English Paper 2 offers four literary genres, and Grade 12 candidates must choose two setworks from poetry, drama, short stories, or novels. Paper 2 assesses candidates' literary competence, which is defined by Brumfit and Carter (1986, p.18), as an 'interesting combination of linguistic, socio-cultural, historical, and semiotic awareness.' In this context, the English literature paper is studied as part of the curriculum that seeks to impart school leaving language competence in addition to Paper 1, which offers a comprehension passage, summary writing, and grammar, while Paper 3 examines transactional writing. English language is not only an object of study, but it is also a Language of Learning and Teaching (LoLT). The knowledge of English helps learners to be able to read and understand the literature texts, as Hismanoglu (2005) states that literature provides learners with a wide range of individual lexical or syntactic items.

Carter and McRae (2014) recommend the integration between language and literature. This is significant in this paper as literature is not an end unto itself, but also serves as a content through which other language skills are transmitted. Moreover, Obediat (1997), as cited by Keshavarzi (2012), states that literature helps students acquire a native-like competence in English, express their ideas in good English, learn the features of modern English, and learn how the English linguistic system is used for communication. Therefore, the learners' literary competence would aid in their linguistic competence. With that in mind, the learners still need a grasp of the language to understand the literary texts. Learners need to be familiar with using English, as Khatib and Seyyedrezaie (2017) posit that literature has been discovered as a valuable and interesting material for improving students' language ability. Sage (1987), as cited by Khatib and Seyyedrezaie (2017), states that he believes that literature-based programmes focus on the interpretation of the language, and this allows the students to experiment with the language. This also emphasises the role that literature can play in the English classroom. However, the study of English literature in Grade 12 seems to be a challenge in some rural schools as highlighted in the problem statement below. There are many factors that could contribute to the good and poor performance of learners in English literature. A study by Gulnaz, Ahmad and Mandoub (2016) identified factors like teachers' teaching styles and practices in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) classrooms, teachers' behaviour and methods of teaching, mismatches between the curriculum and the level as well as the needs of the learners. The participants in the current study were English Second Language (ESL) learners, who are in constant contact with the English language, not EFL learners.

Problem Statement

The main problem is learners' poor performance in the English First Additional Language literature paper in the national examination. According to the data presented in the National Senior Certificate Diagnostic Report Part 2, 2019, English FAL Paper 2 was passed at 46%. The average percentages for the different genres were as follows: *Cry, The Beloved Country* and *Dr Jekyll and Mr Hyde* (novels) obtained 40% and 39%, respectively;

Macbeth 60%, and *My Children! My Africa!* (drama) 60% and 51%, respectively; Short Stories obtained 40%, while Poetry obtained 41%. The disclaimer on the report is that 'the graph is based on data from a random sample of candidates. While this graph might not accurately reflect national averages, it is useful in assessing the relative degree of challenge of each question as experienced by candidates. This report portrays a dire situation in the light of literary competence, from national to circuit level. This failure rate in literature can be attributed to various factors. For example, Ghazali (2008) intimates that students' attitudes towards literature correlate with their proficiency level, which, in turn, is linked to the location of schools. The above report also specifies that candidates need to go beyond identifying literary devices, and comment on how they enhance the texts; teachers need to teach characterisation in context and learners must be able to substantiate their assessment of characters; last, candidates are discouraged from memorising themes without demonstrating insight (ibid, p28). While the report portrays a bigger picture from the perspectives of examination authorities, this study sought to determine from teachers and learners where the problem of poor literary competence emanated from.

Research questions

1. What are the factors that impede English literary competence in five rural schools in Umlalazi circuit?
2. What challenges do Grade 12 teachers and learners in five rural schools in Umlalazi circuit encounter when dealing the literature paper?

Theoretical Framework

Corley and Gioia (2011) posit that a theory is a statement of concepts and their interrelationships that show why a phenomenon occurs. The theoretical framework is the structure that can hold or support a theory of a study (Abend, 2008 & Swanson, 2013). This study hinged on literary competence and the primary participants were learners who were the readers of the literary pieces; therefore, the reader-response theory was most pertinent. The teachers' responses were only important insofar as they shed light on learners' readings of different genres. According to Cahill (1996), there are various reader-response theories which include the transactional, subjective, psychological, and social reader-response theories.

This study was based on the Transactional reader-response theory. As outlined by Tyson (2006), the transactional reader-response theory is led by Loise Rosenblatt and is supported by Wolfgang Iser. This theory involves a transaction between the text's inferred meaning and the individual interpretation by the readers who are influenced by their personal emotions and knowledge. According to Marhaeni (2016), the transactional theory signifies that both the reader and the text play important roles in the formation of meaning. Marhaeni further states that meaning is produced by the continuous transaction between the reader and the text, employing the meaning potential of the text, and the readers' experiential reservoir. According to Cahill (1996), reader-response criticism argues that literature should be viewed as a performing art in which each reader creates their own, possibly unique, text.

Literature Review

The research area of literary studies has traditionally been dominated by literary criticism with less focus on the inexperienced readers and their teachers. This review pays attention to the studies that bring the latter groups to the fore with the aim of understanding the challenges they may be experiencing in the process of literary engagement.

Language used in a text

Some studies have highlighted figurative language used in literary texts as responsible for the difficulties some readers experience. Rhamani (2018) sought to establish problems faced by students of English as a foreign language in reading literary works. The results showed that the learners needed to have enough knowledge of scheme and trope. Another study by Shakfa (2012) reported that students perceived English literature to be difficult because of its complex syntactic structure, and in addition to frequent use of metaphors and other literary devices.

It is not just the figurative language that is an issue, but also the language in general determines literary competence. According to Yunus and Suliman (2014), English literature instructors as well as students find it difficult to understand and appreciate literature texts, especially, if the students lack in terms of language repertoire. A study which was conducted by Olson and Land (2007) revealed several problems regarding the use of literature in the language classroom, including linguistic difficulty and cultural alienation; and literary texts in the study did not benefit the interests of learners. Alem (2011) mentioned that some teachers and students argued that literary texts might be complicated as they include difficult words that influence the whole understanding. Furthermore, Isikli and Tarakci (2017) found that the low proficiency level of participants was the most influential factor that prevented them from studying the literature course successfully. Hussein and Al-Emami (2016) found three main problems affecting productivity of the teaching-learning process. They included

language proficiency level of students, linguistic and stylistic degree of difficulty of the texts, and the degree of cultural (un) familiarity

How texts are perceived

Readers' attitudes towards a text also determine whether the reception of a text will be good or not. This is confirmed by Al-Mahrooqi and Al-Wahaibi (2012) who mention that one important perspective that plays a crucial role in defining and identifying the challenges encountered in English literature is the students' perception of literature studying. Nelson, et al. (2019) foregrounds the attitude to learn and teach literature courses as determiners of a successful engagement with literature. The other set of challenges outlined in this study include students' lack of critical thinking skills and failure to grasp the abstract nature of some literature courses.

Choice of literary a text and its cultural relevance

Wasti (2016) also conducted a study that revealed that the participants' lack of prior linguistic competence and intercultural awareness may challenge their ability to understand and comprehend some references of foreign cultures and vocabulary items used in the classical literary texts taught in the context of this study. Moreover, Novianti's (2016) findings showed that the main considerations to select the literary texts were the length, level of language difficulty, canonical status, and cultural background. Meanwhile Antika (2016) suggested the use of poems as a reading material in the classroom and that poems chosen should be appropriate to the students' ages, comprehension, and interests. Furthermore, Hoff (2017) explored opportunities and challenges related to the fostering of competent "intercultural readers" in foreign language (FL) educational contexts by examining how notions of interculturality were implicated in the teaching materials and classroom discourse. The analysis indicates that the examined text interpretation processes rely on a complex interplay between literary texts, tasks and classroom participants in such respect. Two strands of the analysis pertaining to how issues of intertextuality and the emotional dimension of literary reading play a role in the data are highlighted. In addition, the interpretation of a text relies on an individual. An individual's background and beliefs may have an effect on how one understands the literary text. The actual written text and the reader's feelings play a major role in teaching and learning of literary texts.

Role of the teacher

The study by Wasti (2016) revealed that the role of teachers may be important in utilising literary texts according to the interests and learning needs of their students. Moreover, Afifudin (2017) further states that the teacher must serve as a mediator and motivator to help learners acquire critical thinking processes, gradually, such as reasoning, inferring meaning, finding relationships among literary elements, and giving reasonable opinions about what they read.

Mustofa and Hill (2018) postulate that there should be a synergy between teachers' creativity and students' active participation or recognising words and concepts, researching the ideas related to the context, analysing the author's style, investigating the social issues and events of time that it was written, and comparing the text to other texts.

Other factors

Furthermore, Alshammari, Ahmed and Shouk (2020) conducted a study that outlined six main challenges that might discourage EFL learners from studying English literature. The outlined challenges are literature inherited difficulty, learners' cultural misperceptions, learners' negative attitudes, learners' intrinsic demotivating factors, unfamiliarity/ learners' poor prior knowledge, and instructional difficulty. Mart (2019) mentions that it is worth noting that active reading, emotional and intellectual participation in the text, construction of meaning and elicitation of responses are major aspects of literature discussions. Meanwhile Alfauzan and Hussain (2017) suggest that learners' social environment (family, friends, classmates, teachers, etc.) significantly contribute to constructing positive attitudes and enhancing their perception towards literature as a medium of second language. Furthermore, Li, Wu and Li (2019) highlight that the literary work reading time and quantity should be adequate for college students. Lastly, the research paper by Shalan (2017) investigated the development of the 'literary competence of the EFL learners at 3 universities within Duhok Governorate area during the academic-year 2014-2015. The findings of this study indicate that EFL tertiary level students have got a very poor literary competence; EFL tertiary level students' literary competence should have been acquired during the pre-college learning levels through reading of the mother-tongue's literature, and then could be developed through reading the EFL literature.

In nutshell, the literature suggests several avenues to explore when engaging the phenomenon of literary competence. The current literature mostly focuses on the EFL context, while this study focuses on English as a second language ESL (now referred to as first additional language or abbreviated as EFAL) within rural contexts. Rurality in Umlalazi circuit is generally fraught with a lack of teaching resources. Therefore, while the studies above do provide some insights into literary competence, the uniqueness of the target population in this study offers newer boundaries of knowledge.

Methodology

Research approach and design

This study adopted a qualitative research approach, which, according to Astalin (2013), is a systematic inquiry which seeks to build a holistic, largely narrative, description to inform the researcher's understanding of a social or cultural phenomenon. Therefore, the educational phenomenon of literary competence was unravelled through the narratives of learners and teachers of Grade 12 Paper 2, sourced through focus groups and individual interviews.

A case study design was followed where five schools were selected from one circuit (Umlalazi). The design was informed by Sagadin (1991), as cited by Starman (2013, p31), who posits that a case study is 'used when we analyse and describe ... a group of people (a school department, a group of students with special needs, teaching staff, etc.), individual institutions or a problem (or several problems), process, phenomenon or event in a particular institution, etc. in detail.' The primary participants were learners, while the views of teachers assisted in the triangulation of the findings. This provided a rich description (Hancock & Algozzine, 2017) grounded in deep varied sources of information.

Target population and sampling procedures

McCombes (2019), defines a population as the entire group that the researcher wants to draw conclusions about. The target population for this study were Grade 12 learners and teachers from five (5) rural schools under Umlalazi Circuit in the King Cetshwayo District of Education. Furthermore, McCombes (ibid), describes a sample as the specific group of individuals from which the researcher will collect data. This study adopted purposive sampling, which is a non-probability sampling strategy. Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2007) describe this sampling as handpicking participants according to the specific characteristics that are needed for the research problem. The sample, on one hand, comprised of Grade 12 learners doing English First Additional Language from five selected schools. The composition was as follows: School A had six (6) participants (5 girls and 1 boy); School B had seven (7) participants (5 girls and 2 boys); School C had seven (7) participants (5 girls and 2 boys); School D had six (6) participants (5 girls and 1 boy); and School E had six (6) participants (3 girls and 3 boys). Schools B, C and E were doing drama and short stories, while Schools A and D were doing drama and poetry. The home language (HL) for all the learner participants was isiZulu. On the other hand, five (5) teachers who taught English literature (Paper 2) in the above-mentioned schools were selected, as they were learning facilitators to the learner participants sampled.

Data collection procedures

This study employed focus group interviews with learner participants, and individual semi-structured interviews with teacher participants to collect the data. According to Green and Thorogood (2010), interviews are useful to explore experiences, views, opinions, or beliefs on specific matters. Therefore, the learners' and teachers' experiences, beliefs, and insights into the phenomenon of literary competence during the process of teaching and learning of literature were explored. The transcribed focus groups and individual interviews were analysed using thematic analysis. Majumdar (2018) states that thematic analysis provides concise description and interpretation in terms of themes and patterns from a data set.

Results and Discussion

As indicated above, thematic analysis was employed in the analysis of the data obtained from participants. The key questions that informed the data collection hinged on the challenges that both teachers and learners faced when it came to their engagement with the literature paper. Learners were further asked to articulate the affective and psychological aspects of their literary experiences. The most salient themes that emerged are discussed below.

Theme 1: Failure to explain the effectiveness of literary devices

This theme relates to some Grade 12 learners' failure to provide satisfactory responses during assessment, where literary devices are concerned. The finding was that while learners were able to identify similes and metaphors from literary texts like poems, some could not engage at a deeper level with these tropes. The situation was reported by both teacher participants and learner participants. Participant Teacher 2 has this to say:

And another thing [is] that they even struggle to do is the literary devices. Literature is full of literary devices; for instance, let us say they have been asked about irony [as a] figure of speech, so they will always struggle because at their level, we don't just say they must identify the figure of speech. Let me make an example about a simile; a simile is a direct comparison which uses the words like or as. So, when it comes to literature in Grade 12, we do not use straight forward literary devices such as, 'He is like this', so that it will be easy for the learner. But these literary devices are used within the context. So, you have to understand the context. What our learners are failing to do and at some point, they even

fail to identify these literary devices and they even fail to explain their effectiveness regarding the context of the literary text.

Clearly the problem arises when learners must appreciate the context in which the literary devices are used to enhance meaning. Another teacher, Participant Teacher 4, takes this further and states that learners 'contradict figures of speech and parts of speech'. Participant L1, a learner, confirmed the sentiment held by teachers of literature at Grade 12 by stating that:

They give us difficult figures of speech that are not even easy to write, they use bombastic words, for example Onomatopoeia and Euphemism. These two figures of speech are a challenge since we are not used to them even in Paper 1, we only see them in Paper 2.

To the same end Participant L6 states: 'Identifying the figures of speech is a challenge but it's better than to explain them, maybe when you are given a statement and you are asked to explain the figure of speech found in it.'

The finding confirms Rhamani's (2018) indication that scheme and trope influence readers' understanding of literary texts. Shakfa (2012) also attributes literary difficulty to the figurative language. Therefore, the phenomenon impacts not only on learners' performance, but also on the practice of teaching since at Grade 12 level, learners are expected to have developed adequate literary competence to appreciate how tropes enhance the artistic quality of a text, prior to enrolling for university studies.

Theme 2: Answers are not backed by textual evidence

Another finding that emerged from the interviews and focus groups was that learners struggled with open-ended questions. Some learners failed to back their claims with textual evidence. This was particularly prevalent when they had to answer open-ended questions, as Participant Teacher 1 puts it:

One of the challenges that I've encountered is that learners do generalise. Their responses are not mostly grounded to the text.

At times the situation is exacerbated by teachers who may be struggling to demonstrate how to accurately link sections of the text with relevant examples. In this light, the above participant states:

Some of the things that I've noticed is that some teachers, when they do not understand the story or whichever genre, they make examples that are relevant to the teacher, which means that in the end of the day, whenever learners answer questions, mostly in the November/December examinations, they make use of the examples that were made by the teacher in class. Sometimes [these] are not relevant to the text; it is very much important that whenever you teach a story, learners should know the story line-by-line so that even when they are given open ended questions, learners will be able to quote some examples that are being stated in the text.

This is a good demonstration of the fact that literary incompetence does not visit learners alone; teachers are also prone to offer inaccurate interpretations. Worth noting is the fact that this is an observation made by a teacher about other teachers of English literature. One learner participant was grappling with the theme of a literary work:

I have some experiences and challenges on the theme because our teacher told us that when you want to support the evidence that is being occupied by the theme, you need to support with the answers that are relevant...[something] that is taking place in the story (Participant L5).

This finding partly correlates with Nelson, et al. (2019), who point to students' lack of critical thinking skills and failure to grasp the abstract nature of literature as a problem. The significance of this finding lies in the fact that unsupported generalisations reflect poor engagement with a work, thus demonstrating a lack of literary competence. English literature studies at university level puts emphasis on this skill; therefore, learners must be prepared in this literary analysis if they are to succeed beyond high school.

Theme 3: Learner inactivity during literature lessons

It is apparent from the data collected that another factor that impedes literary attainment among some EFAL learners is their non-participation during literature lessons. There is a correlation between active participation during literature lessons and learners' ability to meaningfully respond to questions during assessment.

Participant Teacher 2 states:

So, what I can say is that, mostly, our learners are passive when it comes to teaching and learning because they simply gain the knowledge that you are telling them and just, at some point, don't become active, especially, in trying to explore the events that they come across in the literary texts. ...So, now they are waiting for you to tell them everything as if now you are giving them a scope for the exam so that they will just come up with the information that you just gave them. That is why at some point, just because you can never cram paper 2, they struggle to answer the open-ended questions.

What pervades the above anecdote is that learners expect the teacher to provide information, which they hope to give back during the examination. It is important to note that literature is not about right or wrong answers. Therefore, learners need to constantly test their interpretations of the different sections of the text during classroom engagements. This finding confirms Mart's (2019) assertion that literature discussions should involve

intellectual participation in the text as well as the construction of meaning. Evidently, literary studies is an intellectual engagement that cannot thrive in silence or apathy. Teacher creativity (Mustofa & Hill, 2018) during lesson design plays a huge role in ensuring that learners take centre stage in the unravelling of a text to eliminate what Alshammari, Ahmed and Shouk (2020) call instructional difficulty.

Theme 4: Failure to read literary texts independently

The fourth theme that emerged during data analysis was that some learners for whom English is not a mother tongue fail to read a literary text without the support of the teacher. Admittedly, there may be extraneous factors responsible for the situation, including text suitability to culture, interest, age, etc. of the reader. However, the teacher participant below explains this untenable situation. Participant Teacher 3 has this to say:

Learners do not want to read the text on their own. Even when you give them homework...when they come back, you find that they haven't even read the book. Therefore, I have to start reading the book together with them orally. And then after that, they will try to capture slowly...gradually [and] gradually until they make it.

The same participant is not persuaded that learners are completely out of depth when it comes to language competence; the main issue is that learners are not making an effort:

The challenge is the language barrier since Paper 2 is in a language which not their home language, which is English...It's not that they don't know English, its only that they are so indolent... They dependent on the teacher...They don't even try by themselves to look up the words from the dictionary. They need to be spoon-fed.

Meanwhile, learners have their own reasons for not coping with the required reading. Some learners seem to lose the ability to navigate the plot of the text with the passage of time. For example, Participant L1 has the following to say:

The challenges that a learner can encounter when doing Paper 2 is mostly in drama; [it] is confusing when you are reaching the last scene. So, you can't recall what happened on the first scene. All you need is to remind yourself...reread the story when you have finished.

Another challenge expressed by learners when it comes to reading prescribed texts is the sheer volume of texts they must go through. For example, Participant L7 states:

I think the number of short stories need to be minimised because it confuses us, learners. We are taught too many short stories, maybe about six, only to find that during the final exam there will only be two short stories. Since we are human and not machines, we can't read and master all these six stories. Maybe they can make us read at least 3 stories and that way it will be easier to read and master them.

This finding cannot be directly attributed to any of the studies reviewed in this article. Various factors may be responsible for the phenomenon. For example, the language difficulty mentioned by the teacher participant above may resonate with Olson and Land (2007), Alem (2011), Isikli and Tarakci (2017) who mention the syntactic composition of literary texts as hindering some readers. Reading literary texts in an engaging way requires a reasonable degree of independence. This is necessitated by the fact that immersion in the work leads to better interpretations of that work. To transition from the process of reading to the one of interpretation, readers need to have mastered the plot, character, setting and other basic elements of a literary text.

Theme 5: Affective and psychological factors have an influence on learner performance

The data indicated that learners are sometimes affected by affective and psychological issues which render them unappreciative readers of literary texts. There are topical issues which learners may find uncomfortable, and this eventually creates a negative attitude towards those texts. Participant L6 comments on a play entitled *My Children! My Africa!* which is set in South Africa during the time of apartheid:

Athol Fugard talks about racism, and it is still a sensitive issue in South Africa because we experienced it during apartheid; it evokes feelings where Whites were more privileged than Blacks. You end up not liking drama such that when you write the exam you will be filled with anger.

The issue of racism seems to be thorny among participants and it brings previous traumatic experiences to the fore. Participant L2 states:

What happens in the short stories is that some of the things that the characters go through are similar to the things we [as] learners have gone through. Like in the short story, *The Doll's House*, there are white and black kids, so the black kids are discriminated. You may find that there is a learner who is being abused and/or discriminated in their home and then that learner may end up losing interest in this short story.

Besides racism, participants react negatively to texts that grapple with other issues that have affected them personally. For example, Participant L8 states:

In the short story, *The Last Breath*, what happens here is what happens in our homes, where parents like making decisions for us. Someone who is being abused in their home and also whom they take decisions for, obviously will not love this story because it would bring bad memories and pain they go through in their homes.

This finding correlates with studies on learner perceptions of literary texts as responsible for their reception (Al-Mahrooqi & Al-Wahaibi (2012), and those that indicate the choice of the text (Antika, 2016) as a determining factor to literary competence. However, none of these studies point to the political responses that are engendered by literary texts. This finding is significant as it underscores the reality that readers' reception of a text can render teaching and learning of literature counterproductive.

Conclusions

The foregoing discussion of the findings brings to light that Grade 12 readers of literary texts need to be more immersed in literature studies if they are to attain literary competence. Notably, when learners leave school, they are expected to be competent readers and writers of English as a language of instruction post high school. More importantly, literary competence is foundational to linguistic competence as literature provides a platform for sharing ideas by interlocutors.

This study set out to establish factors that impede English literary competence, and to identify challenges Grade 12 learners and teachers encounter when dealing with the literature paper. The first finding demonstrates that some Grade 12 readers leave the schooling system having not attained literary competence, even though close reading of the text remains focal at high school. Therefore, learners' failure to navigate the tropes is a serious indictment on learner preparedness for university education. Secondly, the fact that learners struggle with supporting their answers to open ended questions with textual evidence is another impediment to literary competence. Literature studies is about contestation of ideas and worldviews. If learners fail to master this skill, teachers need to make a conscious effort to create activities that foster the desired competences in learners.

Affective and psychological factors will always be embedded to a literary text; it takes a facilitator to tacitly notice how learners respond and are affected by salient issues raised by the text so that different perspectives on the issues can be shared in class. Storytelling can be adopted as a cathartic strategy wherein learners retell stories of their lives so that they can heal. This can be part of a transformative pedagogy used by the teacher to make classroom activities permeate to the outside world to bring about post-traumatic healing and change.

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